

Enhancing Pedestrian Route Choice with LLaVa-Generated Description

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Abstract. Pedestrian navigation is influenced by various environmental factors such as safety, comfort, and accessibility, which have been widely discussed in the literature. While navigation applications may consider some of these aspects in their design, effectively conveying such information to users is still challenging. Presenting all potentially relevant factors can overwhelm users and reduce the efficiency and flexibility of decision-making due to interface limitations and clarity requirement. In addition, individual users may prioritize their own distinct environmental features, which highlights the need for more adaptable methods of information delivery. This study proposes pedestrian route description-LLaVA (PRD-LLaVA), which enhances pedestrian navigation by providing route descriptions that convey relevant environmental information extracted from Google Street View images. With an overall accuracy of 87.60% in testing, the model can identify walkability-related factors when guided by structured prompts and fine-tuning. In addition, the generated route descriptions can depict the characteristics and changes in the pedestrian environment. The findings highlight PRD-LLaVA as a promising approach that balances efficiency and flexibility, which provides an efficient solution for pedestrian route selection.

Keywords. Pedestrian route choice, Generative AI, Multimodal learning, Route planning, LLaVA.

1. Introduction

Navigation applications primarily focus on time and distance when generating routes (Mehta et al., 2019). Previous studies have enhanced pedestrian experience by integrating factors such as comfort and safety (Sohrabi et al.,

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2022). While these improvements add value, exhaustively considering or displaying all possible factors for pedestrian choice may reduce efficiency and flexibility. A more adaptable and scalable approach, such as providing descriptions in free-text format, is needed to offer pedestrians relevant information without overwhelming them with excessive details.

Multimodal large language models (MLLMs), which are specifically renowned as vision–language models, integrate vision and language inputs; they present a promising solution by not only generating textual descriptions of images but also interpreting and analyzing visual information (Zhang et al., 2024a). Among these MLLMs, Large Language-and-Vision Assistant (LLaVA) stands out due to its data efficiency and simple architecture. LLaVA has recently been applied to studies involving walkability assessment and street view image analysis. For instance, Zhang et al. (2024b) focused on safety assessment, which revealed a strong alignment between AI-generated safety rankings and human perception. Blečić et al. (2024) used LLaVA to evaluate walkability, which demonstrated high relevance to human expert assessments.

On the basis of these advancements, this study proposes pedestrian route description-LLaVA (PRD-LLaVA), which integrates initial route planning with LLaVA to enhance pedestrian route choice. PRD-LLaVA uses a structured prompt to generate textual descriptions from Google Street View images, which systematically capture key environmental factors such as area type, sidewalk conditions, and greenery. This approach ensures relevant details are analyzed and presented, which improves pedestrian route selection in navigation systems.

2. Materials and Methods

This section consists of two parts: Section 2.1 describes the study area, route selection, and data collection process. Section 2.2 presents the workflow with prompt designs for processing and analyzing street view images to generate route descriptions.

2.1. Study Area and Materials

The study area is located in the vicinity of National Taiwan University, which includes commercial and residential zones, public spaces such as schools, and recreational areas like parks, as shown in Figure 1. Street View images were acquired using the Google Street View Static APIs (Google, 2024). The collections were recorded with a 100-degree field of view, zero-degree pitch, and a heading determined by the azimuth along routes from a current location to its next point. The data collection was conducted between December 2024 and February 2025, which represent a relatively re-

cent time frame. While the captured imagery may not fully reflect current on-the-ground conditions, this study aims to demonstrate the potential of generating descriptive information from route-based imagery. Twenty routes (from 10 pairs of start and end points, with each pair having at least one and at most three routes) were used for training and validation, with a total of 277 images. For testing, two additional routes with the same start and end points were used, which captured a total of 54 images taken at 25 m intervals.

Figure 1. Study area with route information.

2.2. Methods

A prompt design employed in PRD-LLaVA (LLaVA-1.6) with a three-stage process is proposed to generate route descriptions, as shown in Figure 2. In Stage 1, several structured questions identify pedestrian facility types (Figure 3), determine whether pedestrians have dedicated space or must share the roadway with vehicles, and check for obstructions such as parked cars affecting walkability. Six facility types are proposed: brick-paved sidewalk, brick-paved sidewalk with an arcade, arcade only, green-marked sidewalk, no dedicated pedestrian facility, and no facility with obstruction caused by parked vehicles. Then, a pedestrian-focused image description is generated to understand the overall conditions. This stage may include factors that are not covered in the first stage but are still important, such as road signs. Finally, it summarizes the characteristics of walkability conditions along the routes, which provides a concise understanding of pedestrian accessibility and environmental changes. The design ensures that individual image de-

tails are contextualized within the overall route, which offers a comprehensive representation that enhances the understanding of pedestrian accessibility and walkability.

This workflow contributes by training the model to interpret images from the point of view of a pedestrian and by guiding the AI with specific and accessible language, such as “green-marked sidewalk” and “brick-paved sidewalk,” which improves interpretability and consistency. While some of the images originate from a vehicle-based perspective, such as dashcam footage or Google Street View, this choice is driven by the practicality of data collection. These sources are typically more complete and easier to obtain. By contrast, imagery from pedestrian perspective remains relatively scarce and more resource-intensive to collect. Overall, the workflow helps bridge the gap between visual data and human-centered route understanding, which provides a foundation for pedestrian-aware applications in urban analysis and navigation support.

Training, validation, and test data were annotated according to the workflow, which were initially drafted using ChatGPT-4o API (OpenAI, 2024) and manually refined. The datasets of training and validation were divided in an 8:2 ratio, with the final model selected based on the lowest validation loss. In addition, the performance of the model was evaluated using the test data, which consisted of two evaluation routes with the same start and end points.

Figure 2. Workflow with prompt designs for generating route description on test data.

Figure 3. Representative pedestrian facilities: (a) Brick-paved sidewalk; (b) Brick-paved sidewalk with arcade; (c) Arcade only; (d) Green-marked sidewalk; (e) No dedicated pedestrian facility; (f) No facility with obstruction caused by parked vehicles.

3. Results

The accuracy of Stage 1, which classifies pedestrian facility types, is 90.00% for Test Route 1 (35 instances) and 85.19% for Test Route 2 (29 instances). The overall accuracy is 87.60% after averaging the scores across all images from both routes. This accuracy is based on responses to the first question regarding six facility types. Given that each image may contain more than one type of facility, the scoring criteria are as follows: a fully correct answer is awarded 1 point, a partially correct answer is given 0.5 points, and an incorrect answer receives 0 points.

Figure 4 presents representative outputs from PRD-LLaVA, which illustrate its ability to identify various pedestrian facility within testing routes. The first image correctly identifies multiple features, including a green-marked sidewalk, brick-paved sidewalk, and a crosswalk, which receives a full score of 1. This result suggests that the model performs well in well-marked environments with clear visual cues. The second image depicts a shared street space without a dedicated sidewalk, where pedestrians and vehicles coexist. PRD-LLaVA successfully detects the absence of facilities and notes the presence of obstructions, which also scores 1. This finding demonstrates its capability to infer the walking context from the perspective of the pedestrian within the image.

In the third image, the model correctly identifies the brick-paved sidewalk but misinterprets the green-painted garage floor as a green-marked sidewalk, which results in a partial score of 0.5. The fourth image receives a score of 0, which suggests a failure to identify relevant pedestrian features

despite the presence of a brick-paved sidewalk. In this case, the model mistakenly labels the asphalt road as a brick-paved sidewalk. Considering that the image was sourced from Google Street View rather than captured manually, the viewpoint reflects the perspective of a vehicle, which may have limited the visibility of pedestrian facilities.

Figure 4. Representative outputs from PRD-LLaVA, with identified pedestrian facility types and corresponding annotations.

Table 1 summarizes the performance of PRD-LLaVA in identifying different types of pedestrian facilities across two test routes. The model exhibits generally good capability in recognizing clearly defined features and more complex, multi-facility scenes. A comparative analysis of the two routes further indicates that Test Route 1 comprises a greater number of segments with no pedestrian facilities, which offers valuable insights into spatial disparities and the overall quality of pedestrian infrastructure along the routes.

	Test Route 1	Test Route 2
Pedestrian facilities (Correct predictions / total labels)	None: 6/7 Brick-paved sidewalk: 4/6 Green-marked sidewalk: 6/6 Crosswalk: 5/7 Multi-label: 14/14	None: 2/2 Brick-paved sidewalk: 7/10 Green-marked sidewalk: 5/5 Crosswalk: 1/1 Multi-label: 9/11

Table 1. Performance of pedestrian facility predictions on test routes.

The comparison between the written route descriptions generated by PRD-LLaVA is conducted using the same starting and ending points, and includes partially overlapping segments, with images 25–35 in Figure 5 and images 19–29 in Figure 6. The results demonstrate that the model is capable of capturing key transitions along both test routes (Figure 7). The underlined segments reflect cases where the model successfully identified

shifts in land use, pedestrian infrastructure, and surrounding urban form, such as transitions between different sidewalk types, crosswalks, and building environments. Moreover, the model exhibits the ability to detect finer-grained differences between routes. For example, Test Route 1’s Phase 1 mentions the presence of a modern glass building after crossing a crosswalk (Figure 4-5), whereas Test Route 2’s Phase 2 highlights a detailed feature: “green-marked sidewalks ..., become more prominent” (Figures 6-12 to 6-20) reflecting the model’s ability to recognize pedestrian-oriented elements with greater details.

However, the strikethrough text in Test Route 2 reveals instances of over-interpretation, where vehicle-related infrastructure (e.g., overhead structures primarily used by cars) was mistakenly identified as pedestrian-specific features. Furthermore, the content selection could be further improved to better reflect pedestrian-centered needs, such as variations in the distribution of points of interest. For example, Test Route 1 (Figure 5-5) includes a Family Mart convenience store—an amenity that is relevant to pedestrians and contributes to route preference.

Figure 5. Images along Test Route 1.

Figure 6. Images along Test Route 2.

<i>Test Route 1</i>	<i>Test Route 2</i>
<p>Pedestrian route summary: The pedestrian route begins on a tree-lined sidewalk, transitioning to a wide crosswalk leading to modern glass buildings, predominantly of mixed-use landuse. Key features include crosswalks, traffic lights, and sidewalks with trees and planters. The route continues to narrow streets flanked by parked scooters and multi-story buildings, with various shops and apartment buildings, featuring signs in both Chinese and English. As the route progresses, it passes a brick building at a street corner, alongside a sidewalk and bicycle lane, marked by road signs and crosswalk lines.</p> <p>Phase 1: The pedestrian route starts on a tree-lined sidewalk, transitioning to a wide crosswalk leading to modern glass buildings, with a mix of residential and commercial landuse. Key features include crosswalks, traffic lights, and sidewalks with trees and planters.</p> <p>Phase 2: The route continues on narrow streets flanked by parked scooters and multi-story buildings, with a mix of residential and commercial landuse. Key features include various shops, apartment buildings, and signs in both Chinese and English.</p> <p>Phase 3: The pedestrian route concludes with a brick building at a street corner, alongside a sidewalk and bicycle lane, marked by road signs and crosswalk lines, with a mix of residential and commercial landuse. Key features include crosswalks, traffic lights, and narrow streets with buildings and signs</p>	<p>Pedestrian route summary: The pedestrian route predominantly traverses urban areas with a mix of residential, commercial, and mixed-use landuses. Key environmental features include tree-lined sidewalks, multi-story buildings, overhead pedestrian bridges, green-marked sidewalk, and various road signs. The route can be divided into three phases:</p> <p>Phase 1: The initial phase features wide and narrow streets lined with trees, residential and commercial buildings, and sidewalks. Key elements include trimmed shrubs, street lamps, and brick walls.</p> <p>Phase 2: This phase showcases pedestrian bridges, parking areas, and a higher concentration of mixed-use landuses. Environmental features like directional signs, green-marked sidewalk, and fenced areas become more prominent.</p> <p>Phase 3: The final phase presents a continuous urban landscape with tall buildings, road signs, and various landuses. Notable elements include multi-lane roads, construction equipment, and a higher density of residential and commercial structures.</p>

Figure 7. Route description of the test routes.

4. Conclusions and Future Works

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of PRD-LLaVA in supporting pedestrian route choice by generating route descriptions from street view images. The model extracts, summarizes, and conveys key environmental details of route descriptions in textual form. Thus, it provides contextually relevant information for navigation while reducing the inefficiencies associated with exhaustive enumeration. Compared with having only start and end points without intermediate path descriptions or facility information, the generated content can be adjusted to meet individual user needs and preferences. It may also serve as a valuable reference for visually impaired pedestrians, which offers a basis for spatial imagination and decision-making.

In future research, the representativeness of route segment classification can be further improved, and the ability of the model to filter information relevant to pedestrian needs can be more enhanced. On the data side, incorporating more diverse and higher-quality sources—such as points of interest—may help provide richer contextual understanding beyond visual features alone. In addition, where feasible, collecting imagery from an on-foot, pedestrian perspective could help address potential mismatches caused by relying primarily on vehicle-based views such as those from Google Street View. Overall, integrating more varied data with pedestrian-centered perspectives—whether in model training or data preparation—could contribute to increasing the quality and practical value of pedestrian route descriptions.

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